

"AN ARIMA APPROACH FOR PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS OF MAJOR CEREALS IN APMC BARAMATI"

1: Prathamesh Sanjay Balpuri, Department of Agricultural Economics, Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati-413 102 prathameshbalpuri@gmail.com

2: Prof. A. A. Jambhale, Department of Agricultural Economics, Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati-413 102 Email-

3: Dr. P. S. Deokate, Department of Agricultural Economics, Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati-413 102 Email-

4: Prof. P. S. Shitole, Department of Statistics, Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati-413 102 Email-

5: Kiran Sharad Bhosale, Department of Agriculture Economics, Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati-413 102.

6: Sunil Mahadev Lawate, Department of Agriculture Economics, Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati-413 102.

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Abstract:

Cereals are the important staple foods in many parts of the world. The present study was carried out to forecast prices of major cereals in Baramati APMC of Pune district which is foremost district in terms of production and area. The study deals with the analysis of time series data on monthly prices of major cereals, during 2012 to 2022. In this study Box-Jenkins Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average method was used for modelling and forecasting the prices of major cereals. Various model selection criteria such ACF, PACF, Akaike info criterion, Schwarz criterion, Hannan-Quinn criterion, R^2 and ADF test were used for the identification of representative model for forecasting. The results indicated that seasonal ARIMA (1,0,2) for maize and wheat model was the most adequate and efficient model for forecasting the prices of major cereals. Study also showed the predicted midpoint prices of major cereals for the period from 2012 to 2022. It was observed that there is minor fluctuation in the prices of major cereals in APMC Baramati market. Such studies predict the future price behaviour which will be helpful to the farmers to take the suitable decisions in the marketing of their agricultural produces.

Key Words: Price forecasting, Time series analysis, Box-Jenkins ARIMA, Seasonal ARIMA, Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average, Model selection criteria, ACF (Autocorrelation Function), PACF (Partial Autocorrelation Function), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz criterion (BIC), Hannan-Quinn criterion, R-square (R^2), ADF test (Augmented Dickey-Fuller test).

Introduction

Cereals play a vital role in global agriculture and human nutrition, serving as staple foods for billions of people worldwide. Wheat, maize, rice (corn), rice, barley, oats, and sorghum are among the most important cereal crops. These grains are rich in carbohydrates, providing a significant source of energy for human consumption. Additionally, cereals are often fortified with essential nutrients such as vitamins and minerals, making them even more valuable in combating malnutrition and promoting overall health. From a dietary perspective, cereals contribute to the intake of dietary fiber, which aids in digestion and helps prevent various health conditions, including heart disease and diabetes. Moreover, cereals contain proteins, albeit of varying quality, which are essential for building and repairing body tissues.

Proteins and dietary fiber are present in complex carbs found in cereal. In most cases, they are enriched with several vital vitamins and minerals, low in fat, and high in nutrients. They are not only convenient but also provide the much-needed nourishment. Cereals contribute significantly to agricultural trade and production from an economic standpoint. Cereal crops are a major source of income for many nations, both from exports and for domestic consumption. Cereals are also an essential source of feedstock for the livestock sector, helping to produce dairy, meat, and other animal products. Cereals are used in a wide range of culinary applications, in addition to being directly consumed by humans. They are processed into bread, pasta, breakfast cereals, and snacks.

In conclusion, the importance of cereals in both sociological and economic contexts is highlighted by the fact that they are essential to human nutrition, agricultural economies, and global food security.

However, there are not many studies which focus on predicting major cereals prices. Priyanga (2019) conducted different forecasting models, which included Akaike information criteria (AIC), Schwarz information criteria (SIC) and Box-Jenkins, to study the futures price of Cochin market. Naveena (2014) used an autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model. Lakshmi (2019) used ARIMA, ARIMAX and combined forecasting technique. However, the objective of present study was predictive analysis of major cereals prices by using ARIMA approach.

Materials and Methods:

The study was based on the prices of major commodities in APMC Baramati, so APMC Baramati was selected purposively. In major cereals maize and wheat was selected for the present study in APMC,

Baramati. The data required for the investigation were collected from official records of APMC, Baramati, Annual reports of APMC, District statistical abstract and handbook of basic statistics of Maharashtra state. The month-wise data (2012-2022) in respect of arrival and prices of major commodities were collected from the records maintained by APMC, Baramati.

The prices of major cereals were forecasted for the short future in the Baramati market of Maharashtra state using univariate time series models. Agricultural price modelling differs from non-farm commodities and services price modelling due to the unique characteristics of agricultural product marketplaces. Seasonality of production derived nature of demand, and price-inelastic demand and supply functions are some of the unique features of crops. The biological nature of crop production influences agricultural product price behaviour.

For a given time series data, the ARIMA model was used to quantify and forecast future prices. An ARIMA model could predict a value in a response time series as a linear combination. ARIMA model was used, which required a sufficiently large data set, and model parameters were estimated using EViews programming software to fit the ARIMA models. The ARIMA approach was first propounded by Box and Jenkins (1976). The ARIMA models are also referred to as Box-Jenkins models.

Methodology**Box-Jenkins method:**

Box and Jenkins 1976 describe the entire model-building and forecasting process. In summary, they recommend four essential steps: (i) Model-identification, (ii) Model parameter estimation, (iii) Model diagnostic checking, and (iv) Model forecasting. Below are the details of the estimating and forecasting procedure.

Identification of model:

The stationary check of time series data is performed by applying Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. The ADF test is to test for the unit root in a time series. The number of non-zero coefficients in ACF determines the order of MA terms, and the number of non-zero coefficients in PACF plots determines the order of AR terms. Among several ARIMA models, the best-fitted model was used to forecast the major cereals prices using the data from 2012 to 2022. ARIMA models were identified by estimating the initial values for the orders of non-seasonal parameters "p" and "q". These were based on autocorrelation and partial auto correlation functions with significant spikes. As such

one or more models were ultimately chosen at the identification stage, that provided statistically adequate representations of the available data. At the next stage the precise estimates of parameters of the model were obtained by least squares.

Estimation of parameters:

After tentative identification of a suitable model, the next step is to obtain the Least Square Estimates of the parameters such that the error sum of squares is minimum. On the whole there are fundamentally two ways of getting estimates for such parameters. i) Trial and error ii) Interactive method

The Interactive method was used in the analysis for estimating the parameters.

Diagnostic checking:

It is necessary to do diagnostic checking to verify that the model is adequate after estimation of the parameters of a tentatively identified ARIMA model. Examining ACF and PACF of residuals may show adequacy or inadequacy of the model. The minimum Akaike

Results And Discussion

Table 1 ADF test values and best fitted ARIMA models for the major cereals in APMC, Baramati

Particulars	ADF values at the level	p-value	Best fit ARIMA model
Maize	-0.8026	0.000000	ARIMA 102
Wheat	-2.7396	0.000003	ARIMA 102

Table 2 R², C, Akaike info criterion, Schwarz criterion, Hannan Quinn criterion of major commodities in APMC Baramati

Particulars	R ²	C	Akaike info criterion	Schwarz criterion	Hannan-Quinn criterion
Maize	0.410022	7.485152	15.64	15.73	15.67
Wheat	0.200678	9.452631	13.13	13.22	13.17

The results of ADF tests were depicted in Table 1&2 and the ACF and PACF plotted in fig 1 The ADF values of major cereals in maize at level i.e. for original series was -0.8026. The p-value is 0.00 which were found significant at 1 per cent level. In wheat ADF value is -2.7396 and p-value is 0.000003 which were found significant at 1 per cent level.

The monthly average price time series data of major cereals was collected for 11 years (2012 to 2022) for APMC, Baramati in Pune district of Maharashtra state. The collected data was considered for forecasting the prices of major cereals. An ARIMA model predicts a value in a response time series as a linear combination of its own past values. The price of major cereals fluctuates over season due to the variations in production, market arrivals and storage. Thus, modelling and forecasting the monthly price behaviour over the years is of much practical importance. Forecasting involves making estimates of the future values using past and current information. Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, introduced by Box and Jenkins (1970), was frequently used for discovering the pattern and prediction of future values of the time series data. The forecasting models are often written in short hand as ARIMA (p, d, q) where, 'p' describes the 'AR' (Auto Regressive) part, 'd' describes the

Information Coefficient (AIC), HQC and SC criteria and higher R² were used to determine the differencing order (d, D) required to attain stationarity and the appropriate number of AR and MA parameters.

Forecasting:

After satisfying the adequacy of the fitted model, it can be used for forecasting. EViews programming software was used for time series analysis, developing ARIMA models, and forecasting major commodities. Originally ARIMA models were studied extensively by George Box and Gwilym Jenkins during 1970, and their names were frequently been used synonymously with the general ARIMA process applied to time series analysis, forecasting and control. Ansari and Ahamed (2001) applied ARIMA modelling for time series analysis of world tea prices and industrialized countries' export prices. Pravin (2005) applied Box-Jenkins Approach for Forecasting Copra wholesale price series. Shankar & Prabhakaran (2012) used the ARIMA model to forecast milk production in Tamil Nadu.

'I' (Integrated) part and 'q' describes the 'MA' (Moving Average) part. ARIMA model was adopted in this study, which required a sufficiently large data set and involved four steps Model parameters were estimated using R programming software and to fit the ARIMA models. It was done by observing Auto Correlation Function (ACF) and Partial Auto Correlation Function (PACF) values. The Auto Correlation Function helps in choosing the appropriate values for ordering of moving average terms (MA) and Partial Auto Correlation Function for those autoregressive terms (AR). As stationary time series data has ability to forecast accurate results after modelling so the stationarity in said data of pomegranate prices was tested by applying Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. The ADF test is to test for the unit root in a time series. The number of non-zero coefficients in ACF determines order of MA terms and the number of non-zero coefficients in PACF plots determines order of AR terms. Based on the lowest AIC and BIC the Seasonal ARIMA model (1, 0, 2) was found most suitable model for maize and wheat prices.

Forecasting future prices of maize APMC, Baramati

By using candidate ARIMA model, the future prices for 24 months for maize had been predicted and depicted in Table 2 and fig 2 respectively

Table 3 Maize forecasting

Month	Lower limit	Midpoint	Upper limit
	1028.11	2242.66	3457.21
2023 January	1008.50	2251.09	3493.68
2023 February	986.64	2257.80	3528.96
2023 March	964.77	2265.92	3567.07
2023 April	941.14	2272.88	3604.63
2023 May	917.33	2280.80	3644.26
2023 June	892.14	2287.93	3683.73
2023 July	866.67	2295.70	3724.74
2023 August	840.10	2302.95	3765.81
2023 September	813.19	2310.63	3808.07
2023 October	785.41	2317.96	3850.51
2023 November	757.28	2325.57	3893.87
2023 December	728.43	2332.95	3937.47
2024 January	699.23	2340.52	3981.82

2024 February	669.45	2347.94	4026.42
2024 March	639.33	2355.48	4071.63
2024 April	608.73	2362.92	4117.11
2024 May	577.81	2370.44	4163.08
2024 June	546.48	2377.90	4209.31
2024 July	514.86	2385.41	4255.96
2024 August	482.89	2392.87	4302.86
2024 September	450.65	2400.37	4350.10
2024 October	418.11	2407.85	4397.58
2024 November	385.33	2415.34	4445.35
2024 December	352.29	2422.82	4493.35
2025 January	319.03	2430.31	4541.59
2025 February	285.54	2437.79	4590.04
2025 March	251.85	2445.28	4638.71
2025 April	217.97	2452.76	4687.56
2025 May	183.90	2460.25	4736.60
2025 June	149.65	2467.73	4785.81
2025 July	115.25	2475.22	4835.19
2025 August	80.68	2482.70	4884.72
2025 September	45.97	2490.19	4934.41
2025 October	11.11	2497.67	4984.23
2025 November	-23.86	2505.16	5034.19
2025 December	-58.98	2512.64	5084.27
2026 January	-94.21	2520.13	5134.48
2026 February	-129.56	2527.61	5184.80
2026 March	-165.02	2535.10	5235.23
2026 April	-200.59	2542.58	5285.77
2026 May	-236.25	2550.07	5336.40
2026 June	-272.01	2557.55	5387.13
2026 July	-307.86	2565.04	5437.95
2026 August	-343.80	2572.52	5488.86
2026 September	-379.82	2580.01	5539.85
2026 October	-415.91	2587.50	5590.91
2026 November	-452.09	2594.98	5642.06
2026 December	-488.34	2602.47	5693.28

Fig 1 Forecast from ARIMA 102 (Maize)

Forecasting future prices of wheat APMC, Baramati

By using candidate ARIMA model, the future prices for 24 months for maize had been predicted and depicted in Table 2 and fig 2 respectively.

Table 4 Wheat forecasting

Month	Lower limit	Midpoint	Upper limit
		2113.40	2454.32
2023 January	2061.63	2444.65	2827.66
2023 February	2054.81	2463.71	2872.61
2023 March	2028.53	2468.33	2908.13
2023 April	2013.86	2480.21	2946.57

2023 May	1995.18	2488.45	2981.72
2023 June	1979.88	2498.51	3017.14
2023 July	1964.14	2507.66	3051.17
2023 August	1949.68	2517.26	3084.85
2023 September	1935.50	2526.64	3117.77
2023 October	1922.00	2536.13	3150.26
2023 November	1908.88	2545.56	3182.24
2023 December	1896.22	2555.03	3213.83
2024 January	1883.92	2564.47	3245.02
2024 February	1871.97	2573.93	3275.88
2024 March	1860.33	2583.38	3306.43
2024 April	1848.97	2592.83	3336.69
2024 May	1837.88	2602.28	3366.69
2024 June	1827.02	2611.74	3396.45
2024 July	1816.39	2621.19	3425.99
2024 August	1805.97	2630.64	3455.32
2024 September	1795.73	2640.10	3484.46
2024 October	1785.68	2649.55	3513.42
2024 November	1775.79	2659.00	3542.21
2024 December	1766.06	2668.45	3570.85
2025 January	1756.48	2677.91	3599.34
2025 February	1747.03	2687.36	3627.69
2025 March	1737.71	2696.81	3655.91
2025 April	1728.52	2706.26	3684.01
2025 May	1719.44	2715.72	3712.00
2025 June	1710.47	2725.17	3739.87
2025 July	1701.60	2734.62	3767.65
2025 August	1692.83	2744.07	3795.32
2025 September	1684.15	2753.53	3822.90
2025 October	1675.56	2762.98	3850.40
2025 November	1667.05	2772.43	3877.81
2025 December	1658.63	2781.88	3905.14
2026 January	1650.28	2791.34	3932.40
2026 February	1642.00	2800.79	3959.58
2026 March	1633.79	2810.24	3986.70
2026 April	1625.65	2819.70	4013.74
2026 May	1617.57	2829.15	4040.73
2026 June	1609.55	2838.60	4067.65
2026 July	1601.59	2848.05	4094.52
2026 August	1593.68	2857.51	4121.33
2026 September	1585.83	2866.96	4148.09
2026 October	1578.03	2876.41	4174.79
2026 November	1570.28	2885.86	4201.45
2026 December	1562.57	2895.32	4228.06

Conclusion

The study concluded that seasonal ARIMA model (1,0,2) was the best fit for forecasting of price of major cereals in Baramati market of Maharashtra. Also showed the midpoint of the forecasted prices of maize and wheat during the period from 2012 to 2022. Due to high fluctuation in the price of major cereals in Baramati market, the future price behaviour will help the farmers to take the suitable decision for marketing their product and in deciding what to cultivate. The forecasted price will also help to fetch the highest sell price, ultimately resulting into upliftment of socio-economic status of farmers. It can also be applicable to the government or other economic institution to take appropriate measures and steps to ensure and increase the benefits major cereals growers.

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